
COMPARATIVE STUDY ON UZBEK SECOND FOREIGN LANGUAGES CURRICULUM AND THE CURRICULUM OF KOREAN AS A FOREIGN LANGUAGE OF SOUTH KOREA

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Abstract. This article provides a comparative analysis of the curriculum of Uzbekistan and South Korea for teaching Korean as a foreign language in general. Namely, in Uzbekistan it is taught as a second foreign language. In main part objectives, aims, levels and Korean proficiency by level of both curriculums are compared and analyzed similarities and differences.

Key words: curriculum, second foreign language, Korean as a foreign language, Korean proficiency levels, objectives, aims, levels.

INTRODUCTION

This article compares and analyzes similarities and differences the educational programs of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the Republic of Korea. The former is called the curriculum for a second foreign language, which was adopted in 2023 on August 14 by the Ministry of Preschool and School Education of Uzbekistan, and the latter is the curriculum of Korean as foreign language for secondary schools abroad, adopted in 2021 on April 15 by the Korean Ministry of Education.

By order of the President of Uzbekistan, in order to improve the quality of education and reform the sector based on advanced foreign experience, starting from September 1, 2023, in one of the institutions of general secondary education in each district (city), the practice of teaching students two foreign languages and one profession is gradually being introduced²². Korean language is one of the most

²² Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, dated February 28, 2023, No. DP-27 on the state program for implementing the development strategy of new Uzbekistan for 2022 - 2026 in the “Year of care for people and quality education”

popular foreign languages in Uzbekistan, and it is also on the list of second foreign languages taught to students in secondary schools.

Meanwhile, The Ministry of Education of Republic of Korea has established and is promoting the “2021 Overseas Korean Language Education Support Promotion Plan” [table 1] to support countries in the New Southern and New Northern regions to adopt Korean as a regular foreign language subject and teach and learn it²³. The Ministry of Education is carrying out various efforts to expand Korean language education, such as opening Korean language courses in 2,000 schools in 45 countries (based on 2022 materials), developing Korean language teaching materials, dispatching more Korean language teachers, training local elementary and middle school teachers to become Korean language teachers, and supporting the establishment of Korean language education degree programs. Accordingly, the development of a Korean language curriculum is required to expand the adoption of Korean as an official foreign language subject in regular elementary and middle schools in overseas countries.

Table 1

Main contents of the 2021 overseas Korean language education support project basic plan²⁴

Division		2019	2020	2021		2022	
Aims	Expansion of Korean classes	30 countries 1635 schools	39 countries 1669 schools	43 countries 1800 schools		45 countries 2000 schools	
	Teacher support	Dispatch of Korean teachers	56	70		132	200
		Local teacher	-	7 courses		14 courses	24 courses

²³ The curricula of Korean as a foreign language, The Ministry of Education of Korea, 2021

²⁴ <https://www.news1.kr/society/education/4240079>

		training				
		Teacher internship	-	300	400	500
	Textbook and teaching material development	-	-	General and supplementary textbooks		Customized and supplementary textbooks

In many countries, the popularity of Korean language education is evaluated to have surpassed that of other foreign languages, such as Japanese. According to the Ministry of Education on the 22nd, the number of countries adopting Korean as a second foreign language has steadily increased from 11 in 2014 to 23 last year (2023)²⁵.

In particular, in Uzbekistan, the state of affairs in teaching Korean in recent years is as follows (table 1). Based on statistical data obtained from the Korean Education Center in Tashkent, it can be seen that the bulk of those studying the Korean language are concentrated in secondary schools. And this means that more attention need to pay there. This is what prompted the creation of a new curriculum for a second foreign language in Uzbekistan and a curriculum for Korean as a foreign language in Korea.

Table 2

School level	Number of schools adopting Korean language		Number of Korean language education teachers		Number of students taking Korean language education classes	
	2022	2023	2022	2023	2022	2023
Second.s	33	57	60	84	8519	12766

²⁵ <https://v.daum.net/v/20240423050108749>

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Colleges	5	5	8	8	461	461
Univers.	17	18	148	158	6346	5395
Total	55	80	216	250	15326	18662

MAIN PART

OBJECTIVES

The second foreign language curriculum of Uzbekistan targeting inclusively 7 grade students. According to the order of the Minister of Preschool and School Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 209 dated July 17, 2023, it is established that in the 2023-2024 school year, the second foreign language was be introduced in the 7th grade in secondary schools. That is why this curriculum was developed for the 7th grade taking into account the above. During the development and approval of the curriculum for grades 8-11, corrections and changes may be made to the program. While the curriculum of Korean as a foreign language targeting overseas elementary and middle school learners, not for one specific grade of students. It was developed to present detailed and specific competency statements for each specific educational content area so that it can be used actively and flexibly to meet the needs of overseas classrooms.

AIMS

Now let’s compare the main parts of both programs starting with their aims.

The goals of second foreign language curriculum of Uzbekistan are:

- to interest and encourage the study of foreign languages
- to acquire new information about the studied language and culture
- to improve the culture of communication
- to use methods of mental work
- to achieve the development of thinking ability
- to develop basic knowledge and skills, the ability to express thoughts and feelings and solve problems

- to gain an understanding of multilingualism and multi-culturalism²⁶.

The curriculum of Korean as a foreign language targeting overseas elementary and middle school learners and aims for the following goals.

- By building a repertoire of not only own language but also two or more languages and cultures, students can utilize diverse perspectives as a global citizen.

- to perform the role of a social agent in an interactive communication context in Korean.

- to use own knowledge of Korean language and culture to implement communicative language skills, including linguistic, sociolinguistic, and pragmatic skills.

- to lead to various types of mediation and interaction from a multilingual and multicultural perspective.

- to develop an attitude from an intercultural perspective toward Korea and the Korean language.

As we see, both programs have a common feature - attention to multilingualism and multiculturalism. The 21st century is now the era of a ‘global village’ where the world pursues a life of coexistence within one fence. Today, as the world becomes a daily lifestyle due to groundbreaking developments in transportation and information and communication technologies, people have to become a global citizen and exchanges between countries and cultural groups are becoming more frequent, and the need for mutual understanding for successful exchanges is becoming more urgent. This trend of the times is spreading the demand for early foreign language education along with the need for language and cultural education.

LEVELS

In Uzbekistan the curriculum for teaching a second foreign language includes 2 levels (A1, A2). It is divided into elementary (A1) for grades 7-9 and basic (A2) for grades 10-11. A1.1, A1.2, A1.3 for grades 7-9 using the method of the branch approach of the level system of the second foreign language curriculum for the

²⁶ Second foreign language curriculum, for 7th grade of general secondary education, Ministry of Preschool and School Education 2023

purpose of distribution by class level; For grades 10-11, it is divided into A2 and A2+ levels.

In Korean curriculum, it is believed that a grading system that considers the level of achievement is more suitable for flexibly applying the Korean language curriculum to suit the circumstances of each overseas country than a grading system based on a hierarchy of each stage of education (school level, grade), so the grades are as shown in [table 2]. The grading system in [table 2] is a general roadmap that represents the learner's gradual language learning situation and is not absolute. The grading system is divided into three levels: A, B, and C, with A (A1 and A2) being the basic level, B (B1 and B2) being the independent level, and C (C1 and C2) being the mastery level. Classified by (proficient level).

Of course, language proficiency can be said to be a continuum where the boundaries between grades are not clear, as shown in [table 2], and the boundaries are blurry, like the colors that make up a rainbow.

Table 3.

CEFR language proficiency level

source: Council of Europe(2020, p.36)

It is necessary to indicate that both programs are created on the basis of Common European Framework of Reference for Languages as written in them. It is

clearly visible that the Korean curriculum was created for all 3 levels -A,B,C, given that Korean can be studied from primary grades, but since in Uzbekistan in the 2023-2024 academic year, a second foreign language was introduced from grade 7, the Ministry of Preschool and Primary Education of Uzbekistan has adopted knowledge of a second foreign language at a basic A level.

KOREAN PROFICIENCY BY LEVEL

Referring to the previous statement, let’s consider what skills basic level students should have according to the curricula of both countries. The general learning standards for 7th grade in Uzbekistan are as follows:

- ① Can distinguish and write consonants and vowels in the second foreign language;
- ② can read and understand words and sentences related to everyday life, familiar and general topics;
- ③ listening to conversations related to everyday life, familiar and common topics
- ④ can express his /her opinion on familiar topics;
- ⑤ can write and speak on general topics;
- ⑥ can speak in simple terms about Uzbekistan and the culture of the country whose language is being studied.

The basic Korean language level set in Korean government curriculum has the characteristics shown in [table 3]

Table 4

Basic level Korean language skills

level	Korean proficiency
A2	Can understand sentences and frequently used expressions related to areas of immediate experience (e.g. very basic personal and family information, shopping, local geography, etc.). Can communicate while performing simple tasks that require simple and direct exchange of information about familiar, everyday

	issues. Can describe the setting, environment, and pressing issues in simple terms.
A1	Can use and understand familiar everyday expressions and very basic phrases aimed at meeting specific types of needs. Can introduce him/herself and others, and ask and answer questions about personal details such as where someone lives, people they know, and things they own. Can interact in a simple way if the other person speaks slowly and clearly and is ready to help.

Both are aimed at having the skill to understand and express oneself on familiar topics and situations.

CATEGORIES AND ELEMENTS OF THE CONTENT SYSTEM

Uzbek curriculum consist of language skills, cultural studies and country studies components. Korean curriculum consists of three major categories: communicative language skills, multilingual and multicultural skills, and communicative language activities and strategies. The content system of language activities in Korea was organized into two categories, communicative language activities and communicative language strategies, as upper categories. Four categories, including reception, production, mediation, and interaction, were set and organized as subcategories. This is different from the existing Uzbek second foreign language curriculum, which organizes the content system around language skills such as listening, speaking, reading, and writing. In addition, the reception category is not a category that simply encompasses listening and reading activities, and the production category is a category that simply encompasses speaking and writing activities, but is also different in that it is a category that encompasses strategies related to each language activity. Mediation and interaction correspond to newly established categories compared to the existing Uzbek second foreign language curriculum.

CONCLUSION

Based on a comparative analysis of the curriculums of the two countries, it was revealed that they have their own similarities in the goals and standards of students' skills at the basic A level. But in the Uzbek curriculum the level of mastery is limited to the basic A level, while in the Korean one all 3 – A,B,C levels are considered. Moreover, common language skills are named by different terms in the Korean curriculum than what we are usually used to: listening and reading are accomplished through “reception”, and speaking and writing through “production”, but there are also 2 additional categories, such as interaction and mediation. In real life, interactional contexts such as 'understanding conversations', situational contexts such as understanding guidance and instructions, and understanding lectures, also multi-faceted contexts such as reading and writing e-mail, watching TV, and having online conversations, sensory and media-specific context can also be involved in this subcategory. In addition, the mediation scene that transfers the use of language through (re)composition of the original text, such as translation, paraphrase, interpretation, and summary, is also essential and very important in everyday language activities.

REFERENCES:

1. The curriculum of Korean as a foreign language, Ministry of Korean Education, 2021
2. Second foreign language curriculum, for 7th grade of general secondary education, Ministry of Preschool and School Education 2023
3. Saidova M.M. Bilimlarga asoslangan jamiyatda o‘quvchilarga ikkinchi xorijiy tilni o‘rgatishning maqsad va vazifalari. Pedagogik mahorat № 6, 2024
4. Saidova M.M. Integrativ yondashuv asosida o‘quvchilarga ikkinchi xorijiy tilni o‘qitishda Koreya ta’lim dasturidan foydalanishning ahamiyati. Ta’lim va innovatsion tadqiqotlar, 2024
5. Saidova M. Integrativ yondashuv asosida koreys tilini o'qitish metodikasini takomillashtirishning pedagogik shart-sharoitlari. Talqin va tadqiqotlar, № 13(50), 2024

6. Saidova M. Важность обучения второму иностранному языку и современным профессиям, World of Scientific news in Science Journal, Vol2 Issue 6, 2024.

7. Saidova M. Ikkinchi xorijiy tilni o'qitishda ikki mamlakat madaniyatini o'rgatish prinsipining amaldagi tadbiqu (koreys tili dasrligi misolida). Zamonaviy fan va ta'lim yangiliklari xalqaro ilmiy jurnal, Vol 2 Issue 6, 2024.

8. N.Dilova. Uzluksiz ta'lim tizimida “lifelong learning” konsepsiyasini Joriy etish imkoniyatlari//“Zamonaviy dunyo ta'limi: yangi davr muammolari – yangi yechimlar” mavzusidagi Xalqaro ilmiy-amaliy anjuman materiallari, 2024-yil 17-may kuni Andijon davlat universiteti, 46-49-бетлап

9. Н.Дилова Darsda samarali ta'lim usullaridan foydalanishning o'rni va ahamiyati//“Journal of science-innovative research in Uzbekistan” jurnali volume 2, issue 1, 2024. january. ResearchBib Impact Factor: 8.654/2023 ISSN 2992-8869

10. Н.Дилова Oliy ta'limda o'qitiladigan ijtimoiy gumanitar fanlar asosida bo'lajak o'qituvchilarni shaxslararo munosabatlarga tayyorlash mazmuni//“PEDAGOGIK MAHORAT” ilmiy-nazariy va metodik jurnal. 2023, № 11

11. <https://www.news1.kr/society/education/4240079>

12. <https://blog.naver.com/o2423682/222292828554>

13. <https://v.daum.net/v/20240423050108749>